

Tainaron

By Chelsea Gardner, Acadia University

Entry tags: Religious Complex, Religious Place, Greek Religions, Greek Cult, Graeco-Roman, Religious Group, Greece, Hellenistic Religions, Temple

The site of Tainaron, situated on the southernmost point of the Greek mainland, was the location of a sanctuary to the god Poseidon from the Classical-Roman period. The sanctuary functioned as an important place of refuge and asylum in antiquity, for the enslaved and elite alike. Six inscriptions survive from the site that provide evidence for manumission of enslaved persons to the god Poseidon, and several texts attest to the role the sanctuary played as a safe haven for asylum-seekers. The archaeological remains visible on the site today include Hellenistic masonry (rebuilt into a Christian church of the Aghoi Asomatoi) on the promontory, as well as various building foundations and cuttings near the shore. Archaeological exploration has been limited, and so the foundation of the sanctuary is unknown; the earliest written evidence of the sanctuary to Poseidon dates to the 5th century BCE. Tainaron was also the location of the mythical entrance to the ancient Greek Underworld (Hades), a quarry-site for red and black marble, and the gathering place for mercenaries in the final quarter of the 4th century BCE.

Date Range: 500 BCE - 500 CE

Region: Tainaron

Region tags: Greece, Laconia

The location of the sanctuary to Poseidon at Tainaron was located on the southernmost tip of the Mani peninsula, atop the Matapan promontory.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gardner, C.A.M. 2021. "The Oracle of the Dead" at Ancient Tainaron:Reconsidering the Literary and Archaeological Evidence. *Hesperia* 90, pp.339-358.
- Source 2: Friese, W. 2018. "Following the Dead to the Underworld: An Archaeological Approach to Graeco-Roman Death Oracles," in *Round Trip to Hades in the Eastern Mediterranean Tradition: Visits to the Underworld from Antiquity to Byzantium (Cultural Interactions in the Mediterranean 2)*, ed. G. Ekroth and I. Nilsson, Leiden, pp. 215-239.
- Source 3: Tsouli, M. 2010. "Αρχαιολογικός χώρος Ταϊνάρου," *ArchDelt* 65, B1 [2016], pp. 546-552.

Notes: Additional Sources, in reverse chronological order: Mylonopoulos, I. 2003. *Heiligtümer und Kulte des Poseidon auf der Peloponnes (Kernos Suppl. 13)*, Liège. Bruno, M., and P. Pallante. 2002. "The Lapis Taenarius Quarries of Cape Tainaron," in *ASMOSIA 6: Interdisciplinary Studies on Ancient Stone*.

Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference of the Association for the Study of Marble and Other Stones in Antiquity, Venice, June 15-18, 2000), ed. L. Lazzarini, Padova, pp. 163-176. Panagiotopoulou, A. 2001-2004. "Αρχαιολογικός χώρος Ταινάρου," ArchDelt 56-59, B' [2012], p. 290. Sinn, U. 2000. "Strandgut am Kap Tainaron: Göttlicher Schutz für Randgruppen und Aussenseiter," in Ideologie—Sport—Aussenseiter: Aktuelle Aspekte einer Beschäftigung mit der antiken Gesellschaft (Innsbrucker Beitr ge zur Kulturwissenschaft 108), ed. C. Ulf, Innsbruck, pp. 231-241. Schumacher, R. W. 1993. "Three Related Sanctuaries of Poseidon: Geraistos, Kalareia and Tainaron," in Greek Sanctuaries: New Approaches, ed. N. Marinatos and R. Hägg, London, pp. 51-69. Cummer, W. 1978. "The Sanctuary of Poseidon, Lakonia," AM 93, pp. 35-43. Moschou, L. 1976. "Topographie du Magne: à propos de la région du Ténare Κιστέρνες-Άγιοι Ασώματοι," in Πρακτικά του Α' Διεθνούς Συνεδρίου Πελοποννησιακών Σπουδών (Σπάρτη, 7-14 Σεπτεμβρίου 1975) (Peloponnesiaka Suppl. 6), pp. 45-54. Parachatzis, N. 1976. "Ποσειδών Ταινάριος," ArchEph 115 [1977], pp. 102-125. Moschou, L. 1975. "Τοπογραφικά Μάνης: Η πόλις Τάιναρων," AAA 8, pp. 160-177. Henzen, G. 1857. "Tenaro ed i marmi tenarii," Bdl 1857, pp. 154-158.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1 URL: <https://open.library.ubc.ca/soa/cIRcle/collections/ubctheses/24/items/1.0365795>

— Source 1 Description: Gardner, C.A.M. 2018. The Mani peninsula in antiquity : an archaeological, historical, and epigraphic investigation into regional identity. PhD Dissertation, University of British Columbia.

— Source 2 URL: <https://peoplingthepast.com/2021/07/07/peopling-the-past-video-12-chelsea-gardner-talks-about-ancient-tainaron/>

— Source 2 Description: Video: Ancient Tainaron with Chelsea Gardner (Peopling the Past, Episode 12)

— Source 3 URL: <https://cartographyproject.com/>

— Source 3 Description: The CARTography Project (Cataloguing Ancient Routes and Travelers in the Mani Peninsula)

Notes: Pleiades entry: <https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/570702>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

— Yes

Type of excavation:

— Scientific

Notes: This was a rescue excavation only, not a systematic, diachronic inquiry. Results can be found in Tsouli, M. 2010. "Αρχαιολογικός χώρος Ταινάρου," ArchDelt 65, B'1 [2016], pp. 546-552.

Years of excavation:

— Year range: 2007

Notes: Tsouli, M. 2010. "Αρχαιολογικός χώρος Ταινάρου," ArchDelt 65, B'1 [2016], pp. 546-552.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Tree, grove, or forest
- Cave
- Other [specify]: Liminal space (physical limit of the Greek world)

Type of elevation

- Mountain
- Other [specify]: The Matapan promontory is the southernmost promontory of the Taygetos mountain range

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- Yes

Type of feature

- Other [specify]: Quarrying

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

- Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

- Yes

Notes: The Roman settlement of Kainepolis is the closest known settlement; no earlier settlement is known.

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

- Yes

Notes: Tainaron is coastal and located on important Aegean and Mediterranean maritime routes.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

- Yes

- ↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:
 - Yes
- Notes: Tainaron is coastal and thus located on the Mediterranean transportation networks.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - No

- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]: There is a "channel" on the site but it's use is unknown.

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - Yes

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
 - Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Other [specify]: Both/Unknown

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In modernity

– Renaissance

Notes: At least two phases can be seen, a Byzantine church construction and a post-Byzantine church construction

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Poseidon

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– Square meters: 74.75

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– Field doesn't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: It was previously thought that this place was the location of an oracle to the dead but this has been disproven: Gardner, C.A.M. "The Oracle of the Dead at Ancient Tainaron: A Reconsidering the

Literary and Archaeological Evidence" *Hesperia* 90 (2021), pp. 339-358.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Sea God

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This site is the location of the mythical entrance to the ancient Greek Underworld (Hades). Although no communication with the dead occurred at this site (see Gardner 2021), it is entirely possible that visitors imagined that they felt the presence of the dead due to their proximity to the purported entrance to the Underworld.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: This site was previously thought to function as an oracle of the dead, but this has been recently disproven (Gardner 2021).

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

- Other [specify]: Only one bronze votive has been securely identified from this place. Potsherds are visible on the surface, but the extent of the dedications is unknown.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

- No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

- Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

- Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

- optional (rare)
- optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

- Field doesn't know

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

- Yes

↳ Birth

- No

↳ Transition to adulthood

- No

↳ Death

- No

↳ Other

- Other [specify]: Six manumission stelai were found here (IG V,1 1228-1233), where in previously enslaved persons were freed and consecrated to the god Poseidon. This may have been a reason for pilgrimage.

- ↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
 - Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

- Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

- Yes

- ↳ Frequency of festivals
 - specify: Unknown

- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - All members

- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: Unknown

- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

- Yes

|

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: unknown
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: Unknown
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - No
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - No
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

- ↳ Present full time
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:
– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:
– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:
Economic documents, records etc.
– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:
– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Leda Moschou. Topographie du Magne: à propos de la région du Ténare Κιστέρνες-Άγιοι Ασώματα.

Reference: W. Cummer. The Sanctuary of Poseidon, Lakonia.

Reference: R.W. Schumacher. Three Related Sanctuaries of Poseidon: Geraistos, Kalaureia and Tainaron. (N. Marinatos , R. Hägg undefined), Greek Sanctuaries: New Approaches. London:

Reference: Maria Tsouli. "Αρχαιολογικός χώρος Ταινάρου,".

Reference: Ioannis Mylonopoulos. Heiligtümer und Kulte des Poseidon auf der Peloponnes. Liège.: Kernos Suppl. 13.

Reference: Chelsea Gardner A.M.. The Mani peninsula in antiquity : an archaeological, historical, and epigraphic investigation into regional identity. University of British Columbia: PhD Dissertation.

Reference: Chelsea Gardner A.M.. "The Oracle of the Dead" at Ancient Tainaron:Reconsidering the Literary

and Archaeological Evidence.. *Hesperia*, 90(2) doi: <https://doi.org/10.2972/hesperia.90.2.0339>.